

Synthesis and biological activity of 3-aryl-5-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)isoxazoles

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3-Aryl-5-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)isoxazole derivatives (3a-j, 4a-j) have been prepared by condensing 1-aryl-3-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)-2-propen-1-ones (1a-j, 2a-j) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Compounds 1a-j, 2a-j have been synthesized by the reaction of 3-bromobenzaldehyde with different aryl methyl ketones. All the compounds are screened for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activities.

Isoxazole derivatives are associated with wide spectrum of biological activities¹. Hence, it appeared of interest to prepare some new isoxazole derivatives.

The starting compounds 1-aryl-3-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)-2-propen-1-ones (1a-j, 2a-j) were synthesized² by the reaction of different aryl methyl ketones with 3-bromobenzaldehyde/3-chlorobenzaldehyde. Compounds 1a-j, 2a-j on cyclization³ with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate furnished 3-aryl-5-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)isoxazoles (3a-j, 4a-j).

Elemental and spectral analyses supported the constitution of all products. The products were screened for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activities.

Antitubercular activity was evaluated at 6.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in H₃₇Rv BACTEC 12B medium using the Alamar radiometric system. The antimycobacterial activity data were compared with standard drug rifampin at 0.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration which showed 98% inhibition. Compounds having 4-bromo, 2,4-dichloro, 4-chloro, 4-methyl, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl and 4-methoxy showed higher activity than the others.

Antimicrobial activity was assayed by the cup-plate agar diffusion method⁴ against bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungus *Aspergillus niger* at 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration using amoxycillin, ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin and griseofulvin as standards. The antimicrobial activity data revealed that compounds 1c, d, j, 2c, d, f, 3b, c, h, 4f, h, i, j (zone of inhibition 18–20 mm) were active against *E. coli*. Compounds 1c, d, g, i, 2c, e, h, j, 3a, f, 4f (18–21 mm) were more active against *P. vulgaris*, while compounds 1g, 2g, 3c, h, 4c, h and j (19–22 mm) were active against *B. megaterium*. Compounds 1d, i, 2c, f, 3c, d, j, 4b, c, d and f (18–21 mm) exhibited significant activity against *S. aureus*.

X = Br	R	X = Cl	R
1a, 3a	C ₆ H ₅ -	2a, 4a	C ₆ H ₅ -
1b, 3b	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	2b, 4b	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -
1c, 3c	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	2c, 4c	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -
1d, 3d	2,4-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	2d, 4d	2,4-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -
1e, 3e	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	2e, 4e	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -
1f, 3f	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	2f, 4f	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -
1g, 3g	2-OH-5-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	2g, 4g	2-OH-5-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -
1h, 3h	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	2h, 4h	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -
1i, 3i	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	2i, 4i	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -
1j, 3j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	2j, 4j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -

Compounds **1b**, **c**, **2h**, **3b**, **h**, **4a-c** (18–22 mm) displayed maximum activity against *A. niger*.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400 instrument, ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker AC-300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)-2-propen-1-ones (1h, 2h): An ethanolic solution of 3-bromobenzaldehyde/3-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and various aryl methyl ketones (0.01 mol) in presence of catalytic amount of 30% KOH was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. It was then poured over crushed ice and the product formed was crystallized from ethanol: **1h** (78%), m.p. 108° (Found: C, 60.52; H, 4.07. C₁₆H₁₃O₂Br requires: C, 60.56; H, 4.10%; ν_{max} 3044 (CH=CH, vinyl), 2996 (CH₃ sym.), 1676 (C=O), 1259 (C–O–C), 580 cm⁻¹ (C–Br); δ 3.89 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.26 (1H, dd, CH=CH), 7.73 (1H, d, CH=CH), 6.97–8.04 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 316; **2h** (88%), m.p. 95° (Found: C, 70.42; H, 4.75. C₁₆H₁₃O₂Cl requires: C, 70.45, H, 4.77%; ν_{max} 3015 (CH=CH, vinyl), 1663 (C=O), 737 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.26 (1H, d, CH=CH), 7.79 (1H, d, CH=CH), 6.99–8.04 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 272.

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 62–89%): **1a**, m.p. 105°; **b**, 60°; **c**, 185°; **d**, 110°; **e**, 120°; **f**, 150°; **g**, 102°; **h**, 108°; **i**, 80°; **j**, 130°; **2a**, 70°; **b**, 72°; **c**, 100°; **d**, 108°; **e**, 132°; **f**, 158°; **g**, 124°; **h**, 95°; **i**, 80°; **j**, 130°.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(3'-bromo/chlorophenyl)-isoxazoles (3h, 4h): A mixture of **1h/2h** (0.01 mol) in ethanol and anhyd. sodium acetate (0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid, was added to a solution of

hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Then the reaction mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 7–8 h. The product was isolated and crystallized from ethanol: **3h** (69%), m.p. 132° (Found: C, 58.15; H, 3.60; N, 4.21. C₁₆H₁₂NO₂Br requires: C, 58.18; H, 3.63; N, 4.24%; ν_{max} 452 (C=N, isoxazole ring), 881 (N–O, isoxazole ring), 557 cm⁻¹ (C–Br); δ 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.76–8.01 (9H, m, ArH); m/z 331; **4h** (81%), m.p. 130° (Found: C, 67.22; H, 4.18; N, 4.87. C₁₆H₁₂NO₂Cl requires: C, 67.25; H, 4.20; N, 4.90%; ν_{max} 1469 (C=N, isoxazole ring), 829 (N–O, isoxazole ring), 778 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.98–8.03 (9H, m, ArH); m/z 286.

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 56–84%): **3a**, m.p. 154°; **b**, 103°; **c**, 138°; **d**, 84°; **e**, 140°; **f**, 205°; **g**, 133°; **h**, 131°; **i**, 131°; **j**, 107°; **2a**, 122°; **b**, 112°; **c**, 134°; **d**, 138°; **e**, 220°; **f**, 165°; **g**, 120°; **h**, 130°; **i**, 100°; **j**, 156°.

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